

Service Scoping Matrix

Or, Aligning priorities with available resources

Introduction

An essential part of scoping services is understanding the current situation. While there are many ways to achieve this, using a visual representation can help to build consensus on teams and communicate roles and expectations clearly to different stakeholders. In other words, the output is just as important as the process of creating the visual representation.

This process can be completed at any time: as a routine level-setting exercise, during times of change (growth or loss), or as part of a strategic planning effort. Regardless of the timing, it is important to be candid during the process about the reality, and not the imagined or hoped for service offering.

Instructions for use

Identify your Topics / Areas of Expertise and Service Formats

1. Identify the group needed to complete the exercise. Can you complete this in isolation? Does your department need to be part of the development process?
 - a. *Note: this is likely a different group than those that might need to review or 'approve' the visualization.*
2. Identify the topics you support. What are the offerings you (or your team) support? What operations are you part of?
 - a. Examples include: Creating metadata for e-resources; Data management planning; Digitization and reformatting.
3. Identify your audiences - internal and external. Who are the 'consumers' of your services?
 - a. Examples include: Faculty, staff, and students; General public; Library administration; Collection managers.
4. Identify your formats. How do you support your users? By what modes do you offer your services?
 - a. Examples include: Consultations, via email or in-person; Online resources like LibGuides and Research Pages; Partners on a grant.
5. Identify your levels of support. Is there anything you always have? Are there any services you would only offer after
6. Be exhaustive - within reason. You do not have to capture *every* possible service or service format that you or your department has ever offered.

Populate the Matrix

1. Your Services (responses to Question 2) should be listed in the first column. Each Service should be in its own row.
2. Your Service Formats (responses to Question 4) should be listed in the first row. Each Service Format should be in its own column.
 - a. You should also consider if there are additional Service Formats that are only periodically available (e.g., responses to Questions 5).
3. Place a Check Mark in the cells to indicate the Topics you support through the corresponding Service Format.
 - a. For example, if you offer Topic #1 through Service Formats #1 and #3, place a check mark at the intersections (see example below).
4. Place a hyphen (-) in the cells that correspond to which Topics you do **not** support through specific Service Formats.
 - a. For example, if you do not support Topic #2 through Service Format #3, place a hyphen at the intersection.

	Service Format #1	Service Format #2	Service Format #3
Topic #1	✓	✓	✓
Topic #2	✓	-	-
Topic #3	✓	✓	-

Identify Starts and Stops

Sit with the matrix for a day or so. Consider sharing it with a colleague or supervisor to receive feedback on the content. When you have decided it is accurate:

1. Identify your starts:
 - a. What are the Topics that are currently being underserved? These will be hyphen (-) on the matrix. Fill those corresponding cells in with Green.
2. Identify your stops:
 - a. What are the Topics that are being overserved? These will have check marks on the matrix, but the service may be underutilized or duplicative across the organization.

To continue our example above, this might look like:

	Service Format #1	Service Format #2	Service Format #3
Topic #1	✓	✓	✓
Topic #2	✓	-	-
Topic #3	✓	✓	-

You might also use this opportunity to cease offering a Service Format altogether. In our example, Service Format #3 is not used frequently, perhaps because it is no longer a sustainable option (e.g., building a bespoke website for a digital collection). This provides us the data to defend our decision (but said better).

Service Matrix Template

Things We Support (Rows) / How We Support Them (Columns)					
	✓				

Potential Services:

- Data Management and Sharing Plan Writing
- Data Curation
- Finding or Accessing Data
- Dataset Acquisition for Library Collections
- Data Cleaning
- Data Visualization + Analysis
- Digitization
- Metadata and descriptive work
- Documentation creation

Potential Service Formats:

- Consultations
- Instruction (workshops, class sessions)
- Static resources (LibGuides, Webinar recordings)
- Asynchronous work (Completed independently, like data curation)
- Longer-term Project work (More than 4 hours)

